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THE MANAGEMENT OF THE CORPORATE GOVERNANCE MECHANISMS

The paper deals with the role of corporate governance (CG) in managing corporations, with a focus on the CEO and top management team. It argues that while CG is typically viewed as a governing mechanism, corporate managers also play a significant role in managing CG structures and processes. The author presents various activities that managers can undertake to influence CG, drawing on theory and empirical evidence. The paper discusses several CG mechanisms, including capital structure, auditors, and the managerial labor market, and suggests the ways how these aspects can be managed to benefit the corporation. It challenges the assumption of egoism in CG studies, proposing that managers have their own capacity to think and act, including having organizational objectives. In managing corporate capital and ownership structures, the focus is on equity, debt, and liquidity. Equity is highlighted as crucial in representing shareholder interests and managerial discretion. Managers seek to attract beneficial owners through the client effect, shaping the corporation to align with preferred ownership structures. Earnings management practices, like Big Bath, are discussed as influencing perceptions of managerial performance. Interactive governance, involving personal relationships with owners and governance intelligence, is seen as a way for managers to proactively manage governance mechanisms and ownership structures, auditors, boards, recruitment, executive compensation, strategy, structure, and mass media are viewed as governance mechanisms. Overall, the paper argues that effective management of these governance mechanisms can support the interests of CEOs, top management teams, and organizations.

Key words: corporate governance, corporate management, governance mechanisms, management strategies, ownership management

Свен-Олоф Коллін. Управління механізмами корпоративного менеджменту.

У статті досліджується роль корпоративного менеджменту (КМ) в управлінні корпораціями, з акцентом на генеральному керівництві та команді вищого керівництва корпорації. Стверджується, що хоча КМ зазвичай розглядається як механізм управління, керівники корпорацій також відіграють

значну роль в управлінні структурами та процесами КМ. Спираючись на теорію та емпіричні дані автор представляє різні підходи до впливу на КМ. У статті обговорюється складники КМ, зокрема структура капіталу, аудиторів та ринок управлінських кадрів. Пропонуються шляхи управління цими аспектами, які сприяють розвитку корпорацій. Ставиться під сумнів припущення про егоїзм у дослідженнях КМ, припускаючи, що управлінці мають власну здатність думати та діяти задля реалізації організаційних цілей. У дослідженні управління корпоративним капіталом і структури власності основна увага приділяється власному капіталу, боргу та ліквідності. Наголошується, що власний капітал має вирішальне значення для представлення інтересів акціонерів і свободи управління, саме тому керівники корпорацій прагнуть залучити бенефіціарних власників, що формує корпорацію відповідно до бажаної структури власності. Обговорюються практики управління доходами, як-от Big Bath, як такі, що впливають на сприйняття управлінської діяльності. Розглянута інтерактивна стратегія управління, до якої входять взаємовідносини з власниками на основі нових стратегій управління (governance intelligence), що визначається як спосіб проактивного керівництва механізмами управління та структурами власності, аудиторів, радами корпорацій, стратегіями підбору персоналу та засобами масової комунікації. Стверджується, що ефективне управління цими механізмами знаходиться під впливом інтересів генеральних керівників та команд вищого керівництва корпорацій.

Ключові слова: корпоративне управління, механізми управління, стратегії управління, управління власністю, управління корпораціями.

Introduction

Corporate governance (CG) are those processes and structures that discipline the corporation and especially the Corporate executive officer (CEO) and the top management team (TMT) of the corporation (Schleifer and Vishny, 1997). From the point of view of the CEO and the TMT, CG mechanisms are factors in their environment that they have to deal with as part of the duty to perform their assignment, corporate management. It could be claimed that corporate management to some extent deal with how to develop, maybe in cooperation with the board and the main owners, the corporate strategy, but even more, and this is the main focus of corporate management, to implement the strategy (Collin, Ponomareva, Ottosson & Sundberg, 2017). Thus, corporate managers are engaged in managing, not

governing. But, when being engaged in management, they have to consider the environment, how it influences the organization and the implementation process, and how it can be used in order to make the implementation successful.

An important part of this environment are the corporate governance structures and processes, those that influence the strategy and the implementation of the strategy, especially those actors with the duty to implement the strategy, the corporate managers. Thus, even if it appears peculiar, the governance structures and processes, with functions of directing corporate managers, have to be considered by the corporate management when managing the corporation. This is a mutual process where corporate managers are subject to governance, but at the same time subject the governance to their efforts of managing the governance. Later in this paper I will raise the management activities to governance activities by using the concept of 'interactive governance', which is when corporate managers try to influence, or rather, when they manage the governance agents.

In this paper I will present some activities that corporate managers can perform in order to manage, or even to govern corporate governance. The method I will use in order to identify the activities is speculation, in which I use theory arguments and empirical findings, mainly from my own studies and from my own experience from 30 years of studies in CG. But in this paper I will reverse the findings, in a way putting them on their head, so they fit into the scheme of managers influencing CG instead of the normal and traditional causality, how CG influence managers.

I will use the most common way of conceptualizing CG, which is a list of what is considered to be CG mechanisms (Collin & Smith, 2007). Indeed, it can be criticized for being a mechanistic approach, trying to capture what is in essence a dynamic process. However, it is a systematic approach, and it is well aligned to the dominant research of CG. Therefore, the paper is organized in sections where each CG mechanism is considered from the viewpoint of what actions managers can perform in order to manage, or even govern the specific CG mechanism. The paper starts with the mechanism of capital, including both equity, and by that, how it is organized in the ownership structure, then continuing with debt and the cash flow of the corporation, finalizing the section with the concept of interactive

governance. Then the paper continues with the auditors, the board, the managerial labor market, i.e., recruitment and promotion of managers, the strategy and structure of the organization, and ending with a speculation on how to manage the important part of the environment that mass media constitute. The paper ends with a summary and conclusion about the management of governance.

Before starting, one ontological note has to be made. A very common assumption of CG studies performed within the economic paradigm is that of egoism. I make a small deviation from this assumption by assuming that all individuals, including corporate managers, are individuals with their own capacity to think and to act, which is termed opportunism in the economic theories. They are not simple servants with only one capacity and interest, to obey and to follow the incentives. Being selected to the very top of the organization, they are strong acting individuals. With this capacity they can cooperate with the owners and the board of directors, and other important stakeholders. But they can also neglect governance influences or even create resistance. They have themselves individual objectives but since they are managers, and here is the deviation from the assumption of individuals in the economics paradigm, they also have organizational objectives.

An individual can be said to have at least three dimensions that are of interest in governance.

1. We often assume that individuals are effort avoiding. While it appears as if people are trying to not engage but to be lazy, it could also imply an effort to get around governance pressure that the individual do not believe in and think is a bad idea. It is not effort avoidance but governance avoidance.

2. We assume that individuals try to gain wealth, be it material, social or security. A corporate manager is in a prestigious powerful position and have therefore opportunities to gain wealth from the corporation, i.e., from wage negotiations and through incentive schemes. But we also have to consider other kinds of wealth, that are not directly material but could have material consequences. Managers care about social wealth, such as status, and about security, i.e., to have a secure position and a stable income.

3. We assume that individuals enjoy discretion, i.e., to have both capacity and opportunity to act without constraints. But corporate governance are

mainly constraints, which imply that the manager tries to defend itself from the influence of the governance that reduce the managers discretion. In a way, it is not the full intent of the governance mechanism to reduce the discretion of managers. On the contrary, governance imply to create situations of opportunities of corporate development. Therefore, governance do not imply to recruit obedient individuals, but those with high capacity to act and to be capable, which tend to imply independent individuals.

4. Finally, we deviate from the assumption that managers are purely self-interested. Instead, we assume that they have a conception of their duty, what constitutes a good corporation and what is proper management (Collin, 2020). One could say that they have a kind of corporate ideology, indicating what is right and wrong, which they follow, independent of its consequences on the managers wealth.

We will now walk through the governance mechanisms and consider them from the perspective of the managers, and how they can be managed in order to be a positive force for the corporate managers, in their corporate management, to promote themselves and the corporation. Thus, this will be about corporate management, where the management is directed towards managing the governance.

To manage corporate capital and the ownership

The first corporate mechanism to consider is the mechanism of capital which consist of equity and debt, but we also consider liquidity in the corporation in the form of free cash flow. Of those three, equity is the most important capital because behind equity hides those that are called the owners of the corporation, i.e., the shareholders of the corporation, which are those that in agency theory are termed the principals. It is assumed in agency theory and property right theory that the corporation is not only led by them but also created by them. The corporation has therefor to fulfill the interest of the shareholder. This means that the corporate management should be guided by a shareholder orientation.

To manage capital

Equity capital is a powerful party since equity representatives vote on the shareholder meeting and elect the board of directors, in which much of the governance power is residing. However, equity is the main residual

capital, i.e., the party that gets what is left when all the other parties of the corporation has got their compensation, that is, the profit (Fama & Jensen, 1983). The equity does not have a fixed compensation tied to its contract. It cannot claim to receive a compensation when there is no money left, after all the others have got their compensation. This contrast with debt, for example bank loans, that have a fixed compensation, termed interest, that it always has the right to receive. Managers cannot do what it can do to the equity owner, say: “sorry, there is no money left so you have to wait for the next year to see if you get compensated.” It is said that interest never sleeps. It always keeps up a pressure for corporate performance. Pay or go bankrupt, is the principle of debt. The equity capital is much more forgiving, waiting for the good times to come.

With this forgiving attitude managers could prefer to finance the corporation with equity, hoping that the equity will be forgiving or even asleep. But there is a balance since while debt can dissolve the corporation through bankruptcy, equity have the power to make the managers unemployed. In both cases the manager is at risk, but in the case of debt, even the corporation is at risk. Thus, a manager with a duty towards the corporation, prefer equity.

On the other hand, equity is not interested in overinvesting in a corporation because then more of the shareholders equity runs the risk of being lost in case of bankruptcy. Investors are assumed to diversify their risk through investments in several corporations. But managers can argue that higher levels of equity imply better possibilities for them to make good and fast deals, being able to quickly catch a good business opportunity. This means that higher levels of equity increase the corporate managers discretion, which is highly valued by the managers.

This is also an argument for having high levels of free cash flow, that is, cash flow that is not bound to be used for paying the bills of the corporation. The free cash flow can be used in order to perform quick acquisitions or investments, without the need to have negotiations with banks or sell shares of the corporation in order to get the necessary money. Thus, free cash flow, as large proportion of equity increase the discretion of the managers.

While equity is owned by shareholders, they are organized, if the corporation have listed shares, at a stock market. This market put up

demands on the corporation to supply information so shareholders, actual and potential, can make informed decision about investing, keeping or disinvesting in the corporation. Around the stock market there are also parties supporting the function of the stock market. There are analysts, that collect and analyze information from the corporation and about the corporation and create their product, a recommendation of buying, keeping or selling a share (von Koch, Nilsson & Collin, 2015). Corporate managers have an interest, but also a responsibility to deal with investors at the stock market and the analysts. That is performed through indirect action when the corporation distribute information, and through direct action, when the manager has meeting with major investors and analysts.

These activities are part of interactive governance, which is when corporate managers try to influence, or rather, to manage the governance agents.

Corporate managers influence through giving information to governance agents. This information is, of course, not an objective presentation, as it could have been made by a professor in accounting. This presentation is made by a person that has a personal and organizational interest in creating a positive impression of the corporation. Those that receive the information know, of course, that the information is filtered through and influenced by this double interest.

Interactive governance means that while the governance mechanisms are present in order to direct the managers, or one could say, to frame the agents, the managers on the other hand, are also engaged in framing the governance agents through influencing them through the information given (Collin & Smith, 2023). This is an interaction of framing where both parties try to influence the other party. One could say that while the governance actors frame the agents through governance, the corporate managers manage the governance actors through information framing.

To manage reports

One of the major information channels managed by the managers are the financial reports given each quarter and the yearly annual report. It gains higher legitimacy of information accuracy since the reports, at least the annual report, are inspected by auditors. Of course, even here the managers have an interest of framing. Thus, information is given, within

the limitations of accounting regulations and by consent by the auditors, to support the interest of the managers. The accounting regulation that concerns listed corporations in Europe, the IFRS regulation, is intended to give a fair and true representation of the business of the corporation in financial terms, which will support investors decision making. Since accounting contains valuations in order to settle the costs and revenues of the corporation, there are discretion in the creating of the accounting information. This discretion can be used by managers in order to create information that is supportive for the managers and the corporation.

However, one has to realize that this discretion is not always used in order to create an image of 'gold and green forests'. Negative information is also important since it can shape preferable expectations and it gives an impression of credibility. Thus, to hand out negative news could build trust.

The activity of influencing the information given by the accounting system is termed earnings management, thus it is recognized as being part of corporate management (Collin, Ponomareva, Björklund & Krieg, 2022). Earnings management performed in a correct way, i.e., used within the limits of the accounting regulation and inspected by the auditors is a legal action. Indeed, it is an action that is performed by managers in order to support the corporation, but, as studies have found, also to support the managers.

There is one specific action that is a clear act of earnings management. This is the Big Bath (Broberg, Collin, Tagesson, Axelsson & Schjle, 2011). When a new CEO is recruited, corporations tend to report lower profit when the CEO arrives but higher profit the next year. While it can be due to good performance of the CEO, it could also partly be due to earnings management, where write-offs and depreciations are used to lower the profit when the CEO is arriving, and then the next year, for example assets are valued more preferable, giving higher profits. This is positive for the CEO because it indicates that the CEO is very capable of managing the corporation. The profit increase creates trust and power within the organization because everyone sees that the CEO is capable. It also creates trust externally since increase in profit indicates that the manager has been able to improve the performance of the corporation.

Big Bath is, however, somewhat strange since in an efficient market

Big Bath would have no effect since the market will understand the earnings management activities why the activities will not influence the share price. But Big bath exists, and one reason could be that every corporation performs Big Bath, which imply that if a corporation do not perform a Big Bath, they create a negative signal since it goes against expectations.

Big bath is also used when the corporation has losses. Through earnings management the losses are increased since more losses are still losses. That is why you hardly ever see a corporation doing a loss of one Euro. If the numbers are in red, i.e., reporting losses, the color will not change if the red numbers increase, i.e., if the losses increase.

To sum up, earnings management, for example Big Bath, are methods used by management in order to gain power and respect both internally and externally.

To manage the ownership structure

Managers are subject to the ownership structure, but it is also true that the ownership structure is subject to the managers actions. That is what is termed the client effect (Dyl, Elliott and Handley, 2002), which means that a corporation organize itself and presents itself and thereby attract a specific kind of owners. For example, owners with high demand for yearly dividends are attracted to corporation with high yearly yield.

The client effect from the corporate management perspective means to find out what kind of owners that could be the most the most advantage stock owner for the managers and maybe also for the corporation. The question is what these advantageous owners prefer, and the answer will then guide the management in order to dress the corporation, so it attracts these special owners. Indeed, there is a catwalk for the corporations where they show how preferable they are. Ponomareva, Federo, Aguilera & Collin (2022) found that some corporations had a preference to conform to the global good governance norm, at the cost of higher board director compensation.

The stock market presents a specific threat towards company managers. This is the takeover market where potential shareholders can start buying shares and gaining so much voting power that they can influence the board and thereby influence the CEO and the TMT, ultimately fire the CEO. The takeover market is therefore a threat to the security of the CEO, the

TMT and the organization. This could induce the agents to put up fences against the takeover market, for example, poison pills, which are contractual conditions that makes it very costly to fire the CEO, or dominating, long-term owners.

To manage through interactive governance

A corporate manager has strong incentives to have friendship or personal relationships with their owners. This is the more personal part of interactive governance techniques where there is personal interaction between main governance individuals and management individuals. It constitutes an effort from management to get into the social cliques of the owners. It can happen that dominant owners could be families, a single corporation or an investment fund, or a small group of investors, which constitute the dominant coalition (Collin & Smith, 2019). It is advantageous for management to become part of this dominant coalition. It is, however, also advantageous for the investors to include some individuals from the management into the dominant coalition.

If included into this clique, the dominant coalition, then the manager can influence the owners through personal discussions, through dinner meetings, through phone calls and hunting sessions. This personal interaction between owners and CEO's and TMT is the height of the interactive governance since the personal relationships imply that the actors are trying to create conditions for brotherhood relationships (Collin, 1993) or clan transactions (Ouchi, 1979). This occur when there is a group of individuals that have a high level of trust towards each other and therefor can act with high levels of independence, thus supporting the managers preference for discretion.

Another method included in interactive governance from the managers side is to have a system of governance intelligence. This imply to establish information channels where the corporate managers can get information about what owners are saying and communicating at different arenas, and thereby getting an understanding of the owner's thoughts and ideas.

Governance intelligence could be to have contact with individuals that are close to the clique of the owners, if the managers are not themselves in the clique. It implies to be able to identify those that are advisors, the consiglieres of the owners, and even to get in contact with them. By knowing

about the mindset of the owner's consiglieres, the managers can get an understanding of the mindset of the owners. It also implies to have coverage of mass media that could report about the owner's actions in all respects, and to be present at occasions where the owners tend to show up.

Interactive governance, including governance intelligence, contains the intent to be able to understand how the owners are thinking, and even what their plans are, in order to be able to be proactive, i.e., to make management actions before the owner's act, and thereby influence the preconditions of the owners' possible action.

To manage the auditors

An important agent of the shareholders are the auditors. Auditors have access to internal, privileged information of the corporation and their function is to inspect the reported information created by the corporation and to make sure that it is on a reasonable level of accuracy and being trustworthy. Auditors should be independent from both the owners and the management and therefore not possible to influence. This does not imply that it is not possible to manage the audit. Studies have found that the level of independence of auditors could be influenced through making the audit firm consultants to the corporation, i.e., to use the audit firm for non-audit service. While being highly conspiratory thinking, one can imagine that an auditor that realize that the audit firm can get more business from the corporation, for example by offering education or advice help, then maybe the auditor could be a little bit more flexible when it concerns the accounting inspection. While it is formally the owners that decide which audit firm to use for auditing, it is possible for the corporate managers to influence the choice of audit firm and the managers can use the audit firm in non-audit service, thus creating liaisons to the audit firm, and the auditor that can be productive for their interest. Indeed, in studies performed in Sweden, it has been found that audit quality varies among auditing firms (Donatella, Haraldsson & Tagesson, 2019). Normally it is assumed that the Big Four audit firms have the highest audit quality. But studies indicate that this is not always the case. Some studies have found that there is one specific audit firm belonging to the Big Four audit firms that tend to have lower audit quality. While this could be interpreted as a reduced level of audit

quality, it could also indicate that the firm has a more, one could say, customer-oriented perspective on auditing. If the audit firm has an understanding of the situation of the corporation maybe it can be more flexible in their auditing action. If this could be the case, which, of course, all audit firms deny, the corporate managers have an interest in which audit firm that is elected as the auditors of the corporation.

If this is not the case, but auditors are truly independent, then a different tactics could be expected from the management point of view. A rational action could be to stress audit rotation, which imply that the risk of auditors fulfilling a consigliere function (Collin, Ahlberg, Berg, Broberg & Karlsson, 2017) towards the owners will be reduced since there will be less time to build a trust relationship between the owners and the auditor.

Finally, studies have found that high audit cost constitute a signal of accountability towards the corporation and its management. Company managers could therefore have the interest to increase audit costs, not because they want more auditing performed in the corporation, but because the higher costs signals that it is a trustworthy corporation, and the corporate managers are subject to high levels of accountability (Collin, Haraldsson, Tagesson & Blank, 2017) .

To manage the board

The next corporate governance mechanism that we consider is the board. Maybe the most important way to influence the board is through interactive governance where the CEO and the top management team supply a lot of information to the board (Collin & Smith, 2023). It is information that is shaped under the information management idea, which means to give information that can induce the board to conduct preferred actions and decisions, and to give extensive information that create trust since it shows that the CEO reveal much information which supports the boards function of monitoring the CEO and makes the CEO accountable. The interactive governance will hereby create impressions of monitoring since the board thinks that they are monitoring because they receive and process much information, while they at the same time are subject to cognitive framing through information.

Another part of the interactive governance towards the board is to influence the board to perform the service function. One CEO action is when the CEO interact with the chair, trying to promote the chair to have a board that stress the service function. This function is mainly an asset for the CEO. It is neither monitoring nor incentivizing and it is not shaping the actions of the CEO but gives the CEO an opportunity to get more and better information, even wise advices.

To improve interactive governance possibilities the CEO could try to influence the composition of the board. A CEO could prefer what's called dependent directors, which are those directors that are dependent on the firm, on the CEO and the top management team or on the dominant owner. In one case study I performed I observed how a CEO in a family firm, that was not of the family, tried to include the younger family generation through promoting some of the young family generation to be included as directors of the board. It indicated that it was the CEO, not the family owner, that had a structured strategy of nepotism. In this case it was performed with the interest to secure the firm as a family firm since the CEO believed it would create certainty and stability for the firm and its employees. While the inclusion supported the older family members interest, the inclusion was mainly made with the interest to stabilize the corporation.

The CEO and the TMT could try to support what is very fashionably today, diversity. Heterogeneity of directors is a well-supported norm in society, in the practice books and in much teaching. But with diversity follows the risk, or one should say in this case, the chance of increased conflicts and tensions in the board due to contrasting views and competencies, which could consume a lot of energy at the board meetings which will divert the attention from activities like monitoring. Simply put, a board that are engaged in taking care of conflictual consequences of diversity could be expected to have less power and energy to monitor the CEO. Thus, director diversity could reduce the power of the board in relationship to the CEO, thus increasing the discretion of the CEO.

Another composition question of the board is if the CEO should be included as a director with voting rights. The CEO could argue for it's presence at the board as a board member with voting rights since it will

align the CEO with the will of the board. While being true, an inclusion will also make the CEO more capable of influencing the board's decision making. CEO voting rights as a director is an instrument of alignment, but it is also an instrument of power empowerment.

In USA this double-edged sword is present since most CEOs are voting members of the board. Indeed, they are very often also chair of the board and several other members of the top management team are voting members of the board, which makes the board, in the eyes of a Swedish person, a very weak, almost corrupt board. In Sweden, the CEO cannot be a chair and only one from the TMT, typically the CEO, can be a member.

Concerning the board and its decision-making function, one act of governance intelligence is that the CEO and the TMT tries to find out where board decisions are actually being made and where discussions are being held which precedes the decision. Studies have shown that board functions are not always performed at the board meeting but are performed at other governance arenas (Ahlberg, Collin, Smith & Uman, 2023). For example, in family firms many discussions and actual decision making is performed at family gatherings. Being present at these family gatherings is therefore valuable, or at least, to get information from these gatherings.

Finally, it has been showed in board compensation studies (Collin, et al, 2017) that lower board budgets are correlated with weaker boards since it will be hard to recruit the very best directors with a low board budget. Therefore, the CEO could try to influence the board budget and keep it low.

To manage through recruitment and promotion

Next mechanism to consider is recruitment, that is, the internal and the external managerial labor market. Recruitment is maybe one of the most important mechanisms because if the perfect person is recruited, with the same mindset and preferences as the main dominant owner then there is nothing to govern because that person will act as the owner would have acted. However, recruitment of managers, except for the CEO, is in the hands of the CEO and the TMT. One could imagine that internal labor market recruitment would be preferred by a CEO because the CEO can influence who will be selected and how the socialization will be performed.

If socialization is performed in a perfect way it will create very close-knit management teams characterized by brotherhood relationships with high levels of trust and where there is a loyalty towards those that have recruited the person. With this mechanism of internal labor market and strong internal socialization, it is possible to have a high level of diversity, be it on dimensions of competence, gender, and ethnicity, which can be presented externally as supporting the norm of diversity. The group of managers constitute a clan with norm congruence that is capable of exploiting the developmental part of diversity.

To manage executive compensation

Executive compensation is a mechanism that receive a lot of media and research attention (Collin, Gustafsson, Petersson & Smith, 2014). However, there is a low correlation between compensation and firm performance. The reason could be that compensation is indeed incentives to perform, but also incentives to stay in the position. Thus, compensation could be less an incentive instrument than a recruitment instrument because compensation attracts and retains CEO's. Options are very popular instruments and are formally and to the public motivated by it being an incentive. But renegotiations appearing when the exercise price is less advantageous for the CEO indicates that options are probably more instruments of recruitment than incentives.

To manage strategy and structure

Strategy is a very powerful governance mechanism (Collin & Tagesson, 2010). One way for the CEO to manage the strategy is to use emergent strategies (Foss, McCaffrey & Dorobat, 2022). These are actions that are not really part of the strategy but represents small diversions from the strategy. It could be a small investment in some business opportunity, seldom reported in reports and to the board, that slowly grows and grows and then, at one point in time, becomes so big that it has to be included in the formal strategy. It has become a fait accompli.

A stronger influence on the strategy is what is termed strategic opportunism (Collin & Smith, 2007). This occurs when the organization has capacity to redirect and reshape its strategy in order to exploit

opportunities. This is, however, probably not possible to perform without the consent of the board. Then the CEO needs to perform interactive governance in order to get the board to accept the strategic move.

The organizational structure is not very often considered as a governance mechanism, maybe because it is highly internal. It is, however, part of the governance since it can restrict the capacity of the CEO to act. But when we focus on management of governance, the CEO can use what could be called 'divide and rule'-method. That is to create a complex organizational structure that makes it very hard to find out what's going on in the organization. Of course, it is also very hard for the CEO to understand the organization, but the CEO is always present in the organization and have therefore a significant higher level of understanding what's going on in the organization. If the corporation is listed on a stock market, there tend to be an price to pay for the complexity since a complex structure tend to be punished by the stock market by a lower share price.

To manage governance through mass media

Last, but not the least, there is the mass media as a governance mechanism. Most media could be treated the same way as the stock market by supplying a lot of managed information in order to make it possible for mass media to present the corporation in the way that the CEO would like it to be presented, i.e., to frame mass media through information management. A lot of engagement in mass media will give a high attention to the CEO, which could reduce the possibility for the board to fire the CEO.

A high presence in mass media creates also high legitimacy for the organization, if the presence is well managed. This will make it harder for the board or the owner to try to change the organization in a dramatic way. Thus, good mass media management can create security and certainty for the organization, the TMT and for the CEO.

Summary and conclusion about the management of governance

These were my advices how to perform corporate management concerning the management of the governance mechanisms in order to promote the interest of the CEO, the top management team and the organization. While it sometimes can appear as being promoting inefficiency

and to diverge from the responsibility of the top managers, it could at the same time also be considered to be actions by the top management to secure the organization, and thereby supporting the organizations capacity to develop, and to secure the top management team so they can perform their duties toward the corporation.

The notion that there is a conflict between the principal and the agent do not only contain a conflict about wealth distribution between the agent and the principal. There could also be a conflict that is not about wealth, but about substance, concerning how the corporation should be develop. While agency theory assumes that the corporation is only a mean for their principles to gain wealth, it is also possible to consider a different perspective. That is a perspective where the organization is a constellation of interest, where those that we term agents and principles are only servants of the organization that makes it possible for the organization to develop and to prosper. Thus, a constellation of interest supporting the survival of the organization in order to survive as an interested party.

If there is a constellation of interest, carried by different parties, then there is not one single governance problem, that between the principals and the agents, but as many governance problems as there are parties engaged in the corporation. In this case, my advice to the CEO and the TMT is to give ammunition to those that are considered to be those that should obey so they have power to stand against those that demands others to obey their demands. If there are two very strong actors engaged in fighting against each other, that is very negative and consumes energy that could be given to the development of the corporation. But if these parties, due to more power balance, are engaged in discussions and negotiations in order to develop the cooperation between them and to develop the corporation, then my suggested methods of gaining strength as a CEO and as a TMT could be productive means in order to develop the corporation.

My final words of advice for an reflection is this: If you work at a corporation, if you are a director or if you are an owner and shareholder, you should think what your goal with the engagement is: is it purely to give you wealth, to give you security, to give you discretion, or do you have these individual goals while realizing that you and the others are servants of the organization, for its survival and success?

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